

Supplementary material

An Alternative Chlorine-Assisted Optimization of CdS/Sb₂Se₃ Solar Cells: Towards a Unified Understanding Mechanism

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Fig. S1: Impact of $CdCl_2$ treatment and annealing duration on solar cell performance. The variation in (a) V_{oc} , (b) J_{sc} , (c) FF, and (d) PCE for CdS/Sb_2Se_3 solar cells are illustrated, comparing untreated reference cells (Ref) with those treated with $CdCl_2$ and annealed at $400^\circ C$ for different durations: 5, 15, and 30 minutes.

Figure S2 illustrates the impact of the annealing time of the $CdCl_2$ -treated CdS films, annealed at $400^\circ C$ on the PV parameters of CdS/Sb_2Se_3 solar cells. This experimental procedure was conducted based on our previous experience of metal halide treatments in classical $CdTe$ solar cell technology [1,2] and SnS [3] solar cells as well as following the methodology given in the other published articles [4–8]. $CdCl_2$ solution was prepared at 20 mg/ml concentration in methanol and the saturated solution was filtered, and spin-coated on the CdS films at 2000 rpm. These films were annealed at $400^\circ C$ in a tubular furnace for different time durations. The Sb_2Se_3 films were then deposited on top of these CdS films using VTD deposition and the PV parameters were determined from the J-V curve.

As shown in figure S2, this treatment doesn't provide any additional benefit for our solar cells, in fact, it had a detrimental effect on the PV parameters compared to the solar cells without any $CdCl_2$ treatment or any other PDT. These Ref- CdS films were deposited using the CBD method and at the end of deposition time, the films were dried using a hot gun ($\sim 150^\circ C$) later these films were transferred to the VTD setup and Sb_2Se_3 films were deposited. The annealing of the CdS films at $400^\circ C$ for a long time duration in air can lead to the oxidation of the films. This kind of large oxidation of the CdS buffer layer can lead to a lower performance of the solar cell. It was reported in our previous work[9]. A clear trend in decreasing the PV parameters with increased annealing time was confirmed.

Fig. S1: The impact of annealing temperature of $CdCl_2$ PDT treatment of CdS films on a) V_{OC} , b) J_{SC} , c) FF and d) PCE of the solar cells compared to solar cells with no $CdCl_2$ or any other PDT treatment (Ref).

To investigate the impact of $CdCl_2$ post-deposition annealing temperature on the CdS/ Sb_2Se_3 solar cells. The CdS films were annealed in air after the $CdCl_2$ treatment at 200, 300 and 400 °C for 30 minutes. The performance of these solar cells was compared to those without any treatment. Although the performance of treated solar cells was generally lower, it was observed that solar cells with a CdS buffer layer treated with $CdCl_2$ and annealed at the higher temperature of 400 °C exhibited superior performance compared to those annealed at lower temperatures.

In our experiments, we also observed the peeling off of the Sb_2Se_3 films deposited on the CdS films annealed at lower temperature (200 °C) after $CdCl_2$ PDT. During the VTD deposition, the CdS sample was heated to 400 °C. This will act as a vacuum annealing for the $CdCl_2$ -treated samples. This condition likely induced the out-diffusion of volatile compounds from the samples, hindering the adhesion of Sb_2Se_3 films to the substrate.

Overall, CdS samples treated with $CdCl_2$ and annealed at 400 °C yielded the best-performing solar cells among the treated samples. Conversely, shorter annealing times improved the performance of these solar cells (as shown in Figure S2), but they did not outperform the solar cells with CdS films without any post-deposition treatment.

Fig. S2: AFM image of CdS with 1 mM NH_4Cl .

The AFM image of the CdS film on glass/FTO/CdS substrate shows that the CdS grains are well arranged on the substrate with uniform distribution and closely packed structure. Some grains are agglomerated at specific spots. The roughness of the FTO films leads to the agglomeration of some grains at the peak rough spots, this is unavoidable in the case of chemical deposition process. This morphology was consistent across all CdS films with varying NH_4Cl concentrations.

Fig. S3: Time-resolved Kelvin probe measurements in the dark and under illumination by the solar simulator for CdS films at 0, 1, 2, 4, and 8 mM NH_4Cl .

Figure S4 shows the time-resolved SPV measurements of CdS samples in dark and light conditions. As shown in the main data in the manuscript the CdS films with 1 mM NH_4Cl has higher work function in both dark and light conditions compared to the other samples. The lowest workfunction was observed for the samples without NH_4Cl . The SPV calculations were done from these datas.

Fig. S4: XPS spectra of (a) Cd 3d (b) S 2p (c) Cl 2p and EDX (d) of CdS with 8 mM NH_4Cl .

The XPS analysis of CdS films deposited at different NH_4Cl concentrations was conducted to detect chlorine and other components. Peaks corresponding to Cd 3d and S 2p were observed, whereas no peaks corresponding to Cl 2p were detected. This suggests that either chlorine is not distributed on the surface of the films or its quantity is below the detection limit of XPS. EDX analysis was also performed on the CdS films with 8 mM NH_4Cl . However, even in this highly concentrated film, the presence of chlorine was undetectable.

Fig. S5: AFM image of Sb_2Se_3 surface deposited on 1 mM NH_4Cl -CdS.

Fig. S6: (a, b, c, d, e) dark and (f, g, h, i, j, k) light condition work function distribution of $\text{CdS}/\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3$ films with Au contact for 0, 1, 2, 4, and 8 mM NH_4Cl in CdS process. A black dashed line marks the gold contact area in the WF maps. (l) Graph of work function and surface photovoltage evaluated on the Sb_2Se_3 surface and Au contact as a function of NH_4Cl concentration in CdS process. The work function was calculated as the average value from the work function maps. Surface photovoltage was calculated from time-resolved WF measurements.

Fig. S7: Time-resolved Kelvin probe measurements in the dark and under illumination by the solar simulator for a) $\text{CdS}/\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3$ and b) $\text{CdS}/\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3$ with Au contact at 0, 1, 2, 4, and 8 mM NH_4Cl .

Fig. S8: XRD pattern of Sb_2Se_3 films deposited on CdS buffer layer processed with various NH_4Cl concentrations.

Fig. S9: Integrated current density from EQE of $\text{CdS}/\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3$ solar cells fabricated with at various NH_4Cl concentration in CdS films.

References

- [1] N. Spalatu, J. Hiie, V. Mikli, M. Krunks, V. Valdna, N. Maticiuc, T. Raadik, M. Caraman, Effect of CdCl₂ annealing treatment on structural and optoelectronic properties of close spaced sublimation CdTe/CdS thin film solar cells vs deposition conditions, in: *Thin Solid Films*, Elsevier B.V., 2015: pp. 128–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2014.11.066>.
- [2] N. Spalatu, M. Krunks, J. Hiie, Structural and optoelectronic properties of CdCl₂ activated CdTe thin films modified by multiple thermal annealing, *Thin Solid Films* 633 (2017) 106–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2016.09.042>.
- [3] N. Spalatu, J. Hiie, R. Kaupmees, O. Volobujeva, J. Krustok, I.O. Acik, M. Krunks, Postdeposition Processing of SnS Thin Films and Solar Cells: Prospective Strategy to Obtain Large, Sintered, and Doped SnS Grains by Recrystallization in the Presence of a Metal Halide Flux, *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* 11 (2019) 17539–17554. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.9b03213>.
- [4] H. Cai, R. Cao, J. Gao, C. Qian, B. Che, R. Tang, C. Zhu, T. Chen, Interfacial Engineering towards Enhanced Photovoltaic Performance of Sb₂Se₃ Solar Cell, *Adv Funct Mater* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202208243>.
- [5] D.B. Li, X. Yin, C.R. Grice, L. Guan, Z. Song, C. Wang, C. Chen, K. Li, A.J. Cimaroli, R.A. Awani, D. Zhao, H. Song, W. Tang, Y. Yan, J. Tang, Stable and efficient CdS/Sb₂Se₃ solar cells prepared by scalable close space sublimation, *Nano Energy* 49 (2018) 346–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.04.044>.
- [6] L. Wang, M. Luo, S. Qin, X. Liu, J. Chen, B. Yang, M. Leng, D.J. Xue, Y. Zhou, L. Gao, H. Song, J. Tang, Ambient CdCl₂ treatment on CdS buffer layer for improved performance of Sb₂Se₃ thin film photovoltaics, *Appl Phys Lett* 107 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4932544>.
- [7] X. Wen, C. Chen, S. Lu, K. Li, R. Kondrotas, Y. Zhao, W. Chen, L. Gao, C. Wang, J. Zhang, G. Niu, J. Tang, Vapor transport deposition of antimony selenide thin film solar cells with 7.6% efficiency, (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-04634-6>.
- [8] Y. Zhou, L. Wang, S. Chen, S. Qin, X. Liu, J. Chen, D.J. Xue, M. Luo, Y. Cao, Y. Cheng, E.H. Sargent, J. Tang, Thin-film Sb₂Se₃ photovoltaics with oriented one-dimensional ribbons and benign grain boundaries, *Nat Photonics* 9 (2015) 409–415. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nphoton.2015.78>.
- [9] S. Vadakkedath Gopi, N. Spalatu, M. Basnayaka, R. Krautmann, A. Katerski, R. Josepson, R. Grzibovskis, A. Vembris, M. Krunks, I. Oja Acik, Post deposition annealing effect on properties of CdS films and its impact on CdS/Sb₂Se₃ solar cells performance, *Front Energy Res* 11 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2023.1162576>.